

Evaluation of FEV1 and FVC in Pregnant versus Non-Pregnant Women: A Cross-Sectional Analysis**Bhupendra Varlekar¹, Khushbu Patel², Nayan Mali³, Mina D Varlekar⁴**^{1,2,3}Assistant Professor, Physiology Department, GMERS Medical College, Valsad, Gujarat, India⁴Assistant Professor, Physiology Department, GMERS Medical College, Himmatnagar, Gujarat, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Pregnancy involves the maternal body's adaptation to meet the increasing physiological demands of a developing fetus. This process induces numerous visible and subtle changes in the body, and it is one of the prime examples of selective adaptation within respiratory physiology. The objective of this study is to evaluate and compare specific pulmonary function parameters, particularly forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1) and forced vital capacity (FVC), between healthy pregnant and healthy non-pregnant women.

Materials and Methods: A total of 492 women were categorized into four groups (123 each): non-pregnant women and pregnant women in their 1st, 2nd, and 3rd trimesters. The inclusion criteria were women aged 20-30 years, without systemic illnesses affecting pulmonary function, capable of performing pulmonary function tests. Exclusion criteria were individuals with a history of respiratory disorders, healthy women with a history of substance use, and prior history of lung disease. Pulmonary function assessments were performed using computerized spirometry.

Results: A statistically significant reduction in FEV1 and FVC was observed across all three trimesters in the pregnant cohort compared to the non-pregnant group. The study indicates a marked increase in weight during pregnancy, particularly in the second and third trimesters, along with a significant decline in pulmonary function, as reflected by reduced FEV1 and FVC values as pregnancy progresses.

Conclusion: FEV1 and FVC were notably reduced throughout pregnancy. These changes are likely attributed to the mechanical influence of the expanding uterus and the hormonal effects of estrogen and progesterone on respiratory physiology in pregnant women.

Keywords: Forced Expiratory Volume; Forced Vital Capacity; Pregnancy.

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Introduction

During pregnancy, the body undergoes numerous physiological changes that impact various systems, including the circulatory and respiratory systems. Understanding these changes is crucial when providing care to pregnant women, as it helps to avoid unnecessary medical or surgical interventions for normal pregnancy-related physiological adjustments [1,2]. These alterations begin as early as conception and persist throughout the pregnancy. For instance, although there are no changes in the forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1) and the forced vital capacity (FVC) ratio, hormonal fluctuations during pregnancy lead to variations in smooth muscle tone and connective tissue, which ultimately influence pulmonary function [3-5]. Progesterone and estrogen level changes during pregnancy alter the equilibrium between bronchoconstrictors and bronchodilators. Additionally, increased peptide levels affect the properties of connective tissue. Despite these

changes, FVC and FEV1 remain stable throughout pregnancy [6,7]. The diameter of the lower thoracic cage expands by 2 cm, and the circumference can increase by up to 6 cm, abdominal muscle tone decreases, causing respiration to become more diaphragmatic. Moreover, lung volumes and capacities are affected by pregnancy, gradually decreasing as gestation progresses due to the mechanical impact of the growing uterus. Pulmonary function tests may show a 20% reduction in pregnant women. The FEV1 decreases as pregnancy advances, and by the 28th week, it is significantly lower compared to non-pregnant women [8-10]. Studies conducted in India have also reported notable changes in both FVC and FEV1 [11-13]. Research into pulmonary function during pregnancy in healthy women is beneficial for improving prenatal care and avoiding unnecessary treatments for normal physiological changes in respiratory function. Thus, the current

study was undertaken to assess trimester-specific variations in pulmonary function tests and to compare these changes with age-matched non-pregnant women.

Material and Methods

A total of 492 women, aged 20–30 years, were recruited for this study. The pregnant women group consisted of 369 women, with 123 participants in each trimester: 1st trimester (up to 12 weeks), 2nd trimester (13–28 weeks), and 3rd trimester (29–40 weeks). The control group comprised 123 healthy non-pregnant women.

The following inclusion criteria were applied:

1. Women aged between 20 and 30 years.
2. Absence of any systemic illness that could affect pulmonary function (e.g., asthma, chronic bronchitis).
3. Ability to perform pulmonary function tests.
4. Provided written informed consent.

The study excluded:

1. Individuals with a history of respiratory disorders.
2. Healthy women with a history of tobacco, mishri, or alcohol use.
3. Women with a prior history of any lung disease.

Anthropometric data, including name, age (years), height (cm), and weight (kg), were collected. Pulmonary function, including forced vital capacity (FVC) and forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1), was measured using computerized spirometry device. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA (Kruskal-Wallis test), with a P-value of <0.05 considered as significant.

Results

Table 1 presents the baseline characteristics of study participants across different groups: non-pregnant women, and women in their first, second, and third trimesters of pregnancy.

The average age of participants ranged from 21.26 ± 2.37 years in the second trimester to 23.37 ± 3.55 years in the first trimester, with no significant difference between the groups. Height measurements showed minimal variation, with the highest average in the third trimester group (158.25 ± 5.18 cm) and the lowest in the second trimester (148.63 ± 5.12 cm). Weight, however, demonstrated a progressive increase throughout pregnancy, with a significant rise in the second trimester (50.21 ± 6.49 kg, P < 0.05) and an even more marked increase by the third trimester (58.52 ± 5.84 kg, P < 0.05) compared to the non-pregnant group (47.74 ± 5.52 kg).

Table 1: Baseline parameters in study participants

Parameters	Non-pregnant	1st Trimester	2nd Trimester	3rd Trimester
Age (years)	21.87 ± 3.33	23.37 ± 3.55	21.26 ± 2.37	22.81 ± 2.57
Height (cm)	152.68 ± 4.85	152.63 ± 4.80	148.63 ± 5.12	158.25 ± 5.18
Weight (Kg)	47.74 ± 5.52	48.73 ± 5.56	50.21 ± 6.49*	58.52 ± 5.84*

*P Value < 0.05; statistically significant

Table 2 highlights the Pulmonary Function Test (PFT) parameters.

Forced Expiratory Volume in the first second (FEV1) showed a significant decline across the trimesters compared to the non-pregnant group, starting from 2.39 ± 0.55 L in non-pregnant women to 2.01 ± 0.47 L in the first trimester (P < 0.05), and further decreasing to 1.32 ± 0.26 L in the third trimester (P < 0.05). Similarly, Forced Vital

Capacity (FVC) reduced significantly as pregnancy progressed. It dropped from 2.49 ± 0.58 L in the non-pregnant group to 2.30 ± 0.45 L in the first trimester, and further declined to 1.73 ± 0.41 L by the third trimester (P < 0.05).

Both FEV1 and FVC showed statistically significant reductions with advancing pregnancy stages.

Table 2: PFT parameters in study participants

PFTs	Non-pregnant	1st Trimester	2nd Trimester	3rd Trimester
FEV1 (lit/1st sec)	2.39 ± 0.55	2.01 ± 0.47*	1.76 ± 0.28*	1.32 ± 0.26*
FVC (lit/sec)	2.49 ± 0.58	2.30 ± 0.45*	1.90 ± 0.35*	1.73 ± 0.41*

*P Value < 0.05; statistically significant

Discussion

In this study, anthropometric measurements such as age and height did not show any significant differences, but weight exhibited a significant increase during the 2nd and 3rd trimesters

compared to the non-pregnant control group. A significant reduction in both FEV1 and FVC (P < 0.01) was observed in all three trimesters when compared to non-pregnant women. A substantial weight gain in the 2nd and 3rd trimesters (P < 0.01) was found, which is consistent with findings from

an Algerian study by Taleb et al., where notable weight increases were also observed among pregnant women [14].

The response of pulmonary function, specifically FEV1, was analyzed in both pregnant and non-pregnant participants. In this study, a significant decline in FEV1 was observed across all three trimesters compared to the control group. Furthermore, the reduction in FEV1 was more pronounced in the 1st trimester compared to the 2nd and 3rd trimesters. Similar results were reported by Yerneni and Sajja, with FEV1 values significantly lower across all trimesters [15]. Monga and Kumar also documented reduced FEV1 and FEV1/FVC ratios in the 3rd trimester, noting a gradual decline in FEV1/FVC% as pregnancy progressed [16]. Additional studies by Batool and Shakoor revealed a significant decrease in FEV1 during each trimester [17]. Neeraj proposed that the reduction in pulmonary function during pregnancy may be attributed to a decreased alveolar PCO₂. FVC was also evaluated in both groups, with a marked reduction in FVC observed from the 1st to the 3rd trimester when compared to controls, aligning with previous findings. The most significant reduction occurred in the 1st trimester, potentially due to hormonal changes, although further studies are required to confirm this. Research by Sunyal et al. demonstrated decreased FVC in all trimesters, with the most substantial decrease occurring in the 3rd trimester, likely due to restricted lung movement caused by diaphragm elevation and pressure from the enlarged uterus [18]. The decline in pulmonary function tests during pregnancy can be attributed to factors such as decreased expiratory muscle strength, the enlarging uterus, and diaphragm displacement [19]. Hormonal changes during pregnancy result in a reduction in tracheobronchial smooth muscle tone, while the increasing thoracic width, likely due to the growing uterus, prevents significant impairment of large airway function throughout pregnancy [20]. The study included women aged 20–30, encompassing the majority of the reproductive age group. Importantly, only healthy pregnant women without pre-existing pulmonary conditions were included, which provides a useful dataset for future comparisons between normal pregnancies and those complicated by pulmonary diseases.

However, with the rising trend of pregnancies occurring after the age of 30 and the persistence of early pregnancies (below the age of 20) in the country, the results may not be fully applicable to women outside the 20–30 age range.

Conclusion

The current study revealed a marked reduction in FEV1 and FVC among pregnant women compared to their non-pregnant counterparts. The observed

changes in pulmonary function during pregnancy are largely attributed to the mechanical impact of the expanding uterus and the hormonal influences of estrogen and progesterone. It is crucial to account for these physiological alterations when evaluating pulmonary function in pregnant women.

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